

ELIXIR Report of the 20th RDA Plenary

ELIXIR RDA Focus Group

Report contributors

Allyson Lister (ELIXIR-UK), Carole Goble (ELIXIR-UK), Federico Bianchini (ELIXIR-NO), Fotis Psomopoulos (ELIXIR-GR), Gavin Farrell (ELIXIR-Hub), Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (ELIXIR-SE), Marek Suchánek (ELIXIR-CZ), Nick Juty (ELIXIR-UK), Paulette Lieby (ELIXIR-FR), Susanna-Assunta Sansone (ELIXIR-UK), Sveinung Gundersen (ELIXIR-NO)

Introduction

This document has been prepared by [ELIXIR's RDA Activities Focus Group](#) to showcase the synergies and activities of the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) which may be useful for ELIXIR members operating in the life sciences domain. The RDA was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data. The ELIXIR RDA Activities Focus Group has prepared nineteen reports of [RDA Plenary events](#) to date containing overviews of highlighted RDA recommendations and outputs. This report contains highlights from various sessions of the RDA 20th Plenary which took place as a hybrid event in Gothenburg, 21-23 March, 2023. Additional links to collaborative note documents and/or abstracts provided by the session chairs are included.

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About the 20th RDA Plenary

The twentieth RDA Plenary was a fully hybrid event with virtual and onsite participants interacting and accessing recordings of all sessions using the [WhoVa](#) conferencing platform. It was the tenth anniversary event of the RDA to celebrate a decade of research data collaborations and took place in the same city as the first ever RDA Plenary event in Gothenburg, Sweden during March, 2023.

The organisers reported impressive engagement in this year's event:

- 719 participants (489 onsite and 230 online)
- Attendance from 62 countries.
- 7 Plenary meeting
- 46 Breakout sessions

Following this year's successful event the upcoming 21st RDA Plenary is co-located with SciDataCon where both events take place during [International Data Week 23–26 October, 2023 in Salzburg, Austria](#).

RDA Group Acronyms

- Working Group - WG
- Interest Group - IG
- Birds of Feather - BoF
- Community of Practice - CoP

Summaries Section

This section contains shorter highlight recommendations from the event and other key links and information from the various RDA 19th Plenary sessions.

[Highlighted RDA recommendations & outputs](#)

- All Data Management Plan (DMP) support tools presented during the P20 sessions exemplified a particular aspect of **machine-actionable** DMPs: they place the DMP as a central element in an integrated Current Research Information Systems (CRIS). More information:
 - Progressing Machine Actionable Data Management Plans in DMPRoadmap (pg 13)
 - Data Management Planning: where are we and where do we want to be? (pg 22)

Programme & Link to notes

Note: not all sessions listed have reporter coverage given the volume of sessions at the event.

Days:

- **Monday, 20 March 2023** (co-located events)
- **Tuesday, 21 March 2023**
- **Wednesday, 22 March 2023**
- **Thursday, 23 March 2023**
- **Friday, 24 March 2023** (co-located events)

Monday, 20 March 2023

Start	End	Title (and link to report)
8:30	12:00	Insights into the practicalities of collaboration, data and software sharing across the globe
9:00	12:00	RDA Council Meeting (Closed meeting)
9:00	17:00	RDA in Norway: Networking event
9:30	13:00	Progressing Machine Actionable Data Management Plans in DMP Roadmap
12:00	17:15	Global research Commons: Europe and beyond (EOSC Future)
13:00	16:30	DataCite Connect
14:00	17:00	FAIR environmental data for EOSC and the World: Engineering the ENVRI-Hub
14:00	17:30	The WorldFAIR Project's Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
14:30	17:30	RDA & Research Software FUNDERS FORUM (invitation only)

Tuesday, 21 March 2023

Start	End	Title (and link to report)
9:00	10:30	Opening Plenary Session: Welcome to RDA P20
11:00	12:00	RDA Plenary Session: Building RDA for the Future - Celebrating 10 years of the RDA
13:00	13:55	RDA Plenary Session: Building Institutional Partnerships for the Future
14:00	15:30	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 1
14:00	15:30	GORC International Model WG: Reflections and Document Development, The

Start	End	Title (and link to report)
		EOSC Finnish Forum and the Nordic implementations of research commons
14:00	15:30	Practical Approaches to Tracking and Communicating the Use of Research Data
14:00	15:30	Data Management Planning: where are we and where do we want to be?
14:00	15:30	Coordinating mechanisms for making code visible
14:00	15:30	SSIG plenary meeting - Growing international coordination across social science infrastructures
14:00	15:30	Operationalising the CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science (SoRDS)
14:00	15:30	What is happening in the Semantic interoperability realm and in VSSIG?
16:00	17:30	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 2
16:00	17:30	Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG: Infrastructure supporting the FAIR data principles in life science research practice
16:00	17:30	Pathways to a national PID strategy: a guide to facilitate uptake and alignment
16:00	17:30	Working with PIDS in Tools and e-infrastructures: Three concrete examples
16:00	17:30	The Ethics of AI and Data Visitation: Building Blocks for Data Commons and Open Science
16:00	17:30	Automation of LIMS for Data Analysis and Reuse: Joint Meeting

Wednesday, 22 March 2023

Start	End	Title (and link to report)
9:00	10:30	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 3
9:00	10:30	Sensitive data contexts and disciplines: A look at different approaches
9:00	10:30	Defining the roadmap towards FAIR for Machine Learning
9:00	10:30	Data representation in materials and chemicals based on harmonised domain ontologies
9:00	10:30	Expanding our horizons to new disciplines: harmonising on what is core to all
9:00	10:30	Complex Citations in the Earth and Space Sciences: Formulating Requirements for a Demonstration Prototype
9:00	10:30	Computational Reproducibility: What's Next for RDA?
9:00	10:30	Introducing Innovative Indicators to Track Sweden's Open Research Data Objective: How to Measure Progress? Defining Indicators to Track Open Research Data Across Swedish Universities
11:00	12:30	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 4
11:00	12:30	Software Source Code - policy and incentives

11:00	12:30	Promoting synergies between national RDM and data stewardship networks
11:00	12:30	From Classroom to Practice: integrating education and training in handling research data
11:00	12:30	Develop actionable guidelines from the data versioning principles
11:00	12:30	Increasing the positive impacts of journal policies on data sharing practices
11:00	12:30	The Way to FAIR: from data collection to citation
13:30	15:00	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 5
13:30	15:00	Adoption Meeting of the WG on Dynamic Data Citation
13:30	15:00	Data for Sustainable Development (SD) and Responsible Research (RR)
13:30	15:00	Exploring User-Centered Services for Collections as Data at the Library of Congress
13:30	15:00	Evaluation of Research
13:30	15:00	Community Engagement That Works! Examining tools and success stories of pathways to Engagement in Community-led organisations at a global level
13:30	15:00	Practical implementations of the I-ADOPT framework and future directions
13:30	15:00	IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Discussing the FAIR DO Concept
15:30	17:00	RDA Plenary Session: Building Industrial Partnerships for the Future
17:00	18:00	RDA Plenary Session: Building the RDA Community for the Future

Thursday, 23 March 2023

Start	End	Title (and link to report)
9:00	10:30	RDA Plenary Session: Building Platform Partnerships for the Future
11:00	12:30	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 6
11:00	12:30	Recommendations for data repositories to improve data discoverability
11:00	12:30	Libraries' Role in Supporting UNESCO Open Science Recommendations
11:00	12:30	Continuing the Circle of Life of Earth and Environmental Science Data Infrastructure Projects: Maturing PARSEC and ENVRI-FAIR, Beginning New Adventures
11:00	12:30	The Role of Middleware in Data and Metadata Management: National and Institutional Approaches Involving iRODS and Alternatives
11:00	12:30	Data Repository Attributes Working Group (DRAWG) Working Meeting
11:00	12:30	Brokering Framework - Update and Finalisation
11:00	12:30	Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive Data: FAIRness for "Closed" Data and Processes

13:30	15:00	RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 7
13:30	15:00	TRUST Principles & Certification updates
13:30	15:00	Describing diverse chemistry datasets across distributed data resources
13:30	15:00	Draft recommendations for making VREs FAIR and FAIR-enabling
13:30	15:00	Data Granularity Guidance - Going Once, Going Twice,...
13:30	15:00	Improving Global Agricultural Data (IGAD) Community of Practice First Steps and Way Forward
13:30	15:00	Towards implementable recommendations: taking advantage of the SHARC open science
13:30	15:00	Open Science Graph - Interoperability Framework. A debriefing from the Task Force
15:30	16:30	RDA Closing Plenary
17:00	19:00	RDA TAB & WG/IG Co-chairs

Friday, 24 March 2023

Start	End	Title (and link to report)
8:00	12:00	FAIR-IMPACT closed meeting
9:00	16:30	ORCID Consortia Leads event
9:00	13:00	Data-driven life science and the RDA
9:00	12:00	Research Software workshop: guidelines and metrics for metadata curation
10:00	16:00	GORC International Model WG: Model Synthesis Workshop
13:00	16:30	DDI Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI): Optimising Your Data Description for Integration and Reuse

Detailed Reports Section

This section contains detailed reports and key links from the various conference sessions:

- [Monday, 20 March 2023](#) (co-located events)
- [Tuesday, 21 March 2023](#)
- [Wednesday, 22 March 2023](#)
- [Thursday, 23 March 2023](#)
- [Friday, 24 March 2023](#) (co-located events)

Monday, 20 March 2023

RDA in Norway: Networking event

20 March 2023, 9:00 - 17:00 CET, [event link](#), Decibel room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Reported by:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Highlights:

- Trond Kvamme: [RDA Norway, planned activities for 2023:](#)
 - Establishing a "Data champions" task group (led by UiO)
 - Establish a task on Data Protection and Sensitive Data
 - Continue work on establishing a curator network
 - New iteration of the RDM terminology list (broadened scope)..
- Katrine Weisteen Bjerde: [Intro to Skills4EOSC](#)
 - Goal: Advance Open Science skills by unifying the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem.
- Alexander Refsum: [RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies of Rhythm, Time and Motion](#)
 - "Open Research" is not equal to "Open Science"
 - Investigates "rhythm as fundamental property of human life" by setting up MusicLabs where they set up a concert in connection with a workshop, panel discussion and collection of data
 - Levels of working with other disciplines: Intradisciplinary, crossdisciplinary, multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary
- Matthew Granger: [Living Norway Ecological Data Network](#)
 - Provide the society with documented and harmonised data from ecological sciences

- Alexander Refsum: [The Open Science Career Assessment Matrix \(OS-CAM\) and Norwegian Career Assessment Matrix \(NOR-CAM\)](#)
 - Automagic and standardised CV system
- Anathasia Monika Mowinckel: [When we demand too much](#) (of researchers)
 - Arguing for strengthening "Research Software Engineers" as career path
- Emma Lazzeri: [Open Science is the new normal](#)
 - Overview of the Open Science approach and importance in a European context
- Ingrid Heggland: [Data Infrastructure committee](#)
 - Report from committee assigned by the Research Council of Norway from the Ministry of Education and Research regarding investments in the coming Long-term plan for research and higher education
 - How can research data infrastructure be organized for optimal utilization (Highlighted recommendations)?
 - "By 2030 all research fields should have access to data management and curation competency"
 - "Framework for long-term and sustainable funding of national data infrastructure – different service categories and types of funding"
 - "Basic infrastructure at research institution should be funded within regular budgets"
- Ane Møller Gabrielsen: [UB BOTT project report - Data management plans \(DMP\) - national tools and recommendations](#)
 - DMP Online and Data Steward Wizard (DSW) at the top of ranking of DMP tools
 - Assess the need for national instances of DMPOnline and/or DSW
 - Recommend national service providers to look towards established services
 - Should use tools that can generate machine actionable DMPs
- Live Håndlykken Kvåle: [Competency framework for data management in Norway](#)
 - Focus: Academic libraries
 - Report: [Kompetanserammeverk for forskningsdatastøtte i UH-bibliotek](#)
- Phillipp Konzett: [National Curation Network Project in Norway](#)

Notes:

[All presentations from event](#)

Progressing Machine Actionable Data Management Plans in DMPRoadmap

20 March 2023, 9:30 - 13:00 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Paulette Lieby (FR)
- Allyson Lister (UK)

Reported by:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Allyson Lister (UK)

Highlights:

- DMPRoadmap is a common codebase for different DMP tools such as DMPtool (UC3), DMPonline (DCC), DMPOPIDoR, DMPTuuli, PGDonline, and possibly others.
- Once the feature set diverges “too much” from the common one, it is harder to manage (e.g. synchronise changes) and leads to various other challenges.
- There is the DAMAP tool in Austria tailored for integrations with different systems to fulfil maDMP which covers the core of the DMP process (the essential information needed by stakeholders).
- FAIRsharing (an ELIXIR RIR) can (and is currently) used as a content provider for maDMP ([slides \(pdf\)](#), [video recording](#)).

I (Paulette) would add:

- All tools discussed each exemplified a particular aspect of machine-actionable DMPs: DMP as an element in an integrated CRIS

Notes:

The welcome session by Kevin Ashley briefly introduced DMPRoadmap as an international project, the most widely-used system for creating DMPs around the world. It has also been 10 years since it partnered with RDA. The second presentation by Tomasz Miksa was about RDA maDMP WG. He presented the idea to remove the burden of a lot of writing, capturing only the essential information in a standardised and machine-actionable way. The standard strives to remove issues with free text (however there are some free text fields), and stress out the use of PIDs. It covers the whole process of DMP. Newly developed DAMAP tool in Austria for automating and integrating with other systems (e.g. CRIS system of university).

Diana Sisu with Kevin Ashley then presented the overview of the DMPRoadmap Project. The brief history of the project has been outlined: checklist of DCC in 2008, DMPonline v1 launched 2010, DMPTool 2011 (UC3), since 2016 common codebase DMPRoadmap, DMP assistant in Canada since 2016. Anyone can use the shared codebase to build different services (national, institutional, etc.) - DMPonline.be, SUNET, DMPTuuli, PGDonline, CORA eiNa DMP, and others. There are a lot of requests from users, they are afraid of diverging too much from the common codebase. The current priorities are: integration with re3data, FAIRsharing, machine-actionability, plan creation wizard, infrastructure updates.

Maria Praetzelis from UC3 (California Digital Library) presented maDMPs in DMPRoadmap, more specifically in their DMPTool used mainly at universities in California, US. Currently, there is only one project manager (Maria) and one developer (Brian). They currently focus on use of PIDs, maDMPs and

issuing DOIs for DMPs. They are using RDA Metadata Standards Catalog and plan to use FAIRsharing. The connection with DataCite and DataCite Commons (DOIs) is made for issuing PIDs for DMPs, DMPs in ORCID records for creator(s) of DMP; they had to develop APIv2 for system integrations, it is based on the maDMP JSON (but extended). As a future plan, they want to add the ability to upload DMP files created elsewhere to generate PID, admin dashboard, API and integrations. From the questions and answers part, they currently do not cite/credit authors of DMPs, only entire DMP can be private (and metadata public), and for reuse of existing DMPs, the use of API is needed.

Gabriela Mejias presented the role of PIDs in enabling machine actionable DMPs, mainly mentioning the existing report with value proposition for PID stakeholders. There are more plans in this direction within EOSC activities. Laura Vilela Rodrigues Rezende presented the Brazilian implementation of maDMPs (PGD-BR) and described the national service for writing data management plans. This project started in November 2021 and it utilises r3data as well as other integrations related to the RDA DCS for maDMPs.

Diana Sisu presented planned features of DMPonline:ROR integration (affiliation), Research Outputs (additional tab, optional), Grant ID field. Furthermore, currently in specification phase are the following potential features: new plan creation wizard (select the best suitable template), plan versioning. They use and plan to extend the multi-tenant model with possibility of customizations. Allyson Lister explained how FAIRsharing can be used as a content provider for maDMP. The example case used also DSW where a record from FAIRsharing can be selected and maDMP (according to RDA DCS) then exported (see example output in [github](#)). The final presentation by Benjamin Faure provided a brief Overview of maDMP capabilities in DMP-OPIDoR, the national French implementation of DMPRoadmap, mainly its special features: computing data storage costs for DMP, sending notifications, imports for maDMP, and additional tabs (e.g. for research outputs).

Reported by: Paulette Lieby (FR)

My summary:

- *Event sponsors: DMPTool (UC3) DMPOnline(DCC) DMP-OPIDoR (FR) DMP Assistant (Ca.)*
- Overview of the history of the ma-actionable concept to the RDA DMP CS
- Overview of the DMPRoadmap tools:
 - Structured output based on RDA CS
 - API EOSC standard
 - Integration (current or planned) with Datacite, ORCID, r3data, FAIRsharing, rspace (notebook: <https://researchspace.helpdocs.io/article/owwlhlgxnr-dmptool-integration>) with dataverse integration (DMPTool)
 - Integration with storage providers, funders (DMP-OPIDoR)
- Roadmap:
 - ID generation
 - Plan creation wizard
 - Versioning

- Integration with ORCID, Dataverse, r3data
 - An example (Laura Vilela Rodrigues Rezende - Brazilian Implementation of maDMPs) of DMP integration within the system CRIS (see <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3490396>)
-

FAIR environmental data for EOSC and the World: Engineering the ENVRI-Hub

20 March 2023, 14:00 - 17:00 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Reported by: Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- ENVRI is finalising its ENVRI-Hub as the central gateway to environmental data and services offered by the European environmental research infrastructures: <https://hubtest.envri-fair.eu/>

Notes:

Anca Hienola presented the concept of the ENVRI-hub concept. First, ENVRI was presented in general, then the key services, catalogue, AAI, and the hub itself. The following presentation by Keith Jeffery introduces ENVRI Catalogue of Services which provides metadata based on catalogue schema and related services. It is using CERIF (format) and EPOS-DCAT-AP. Currently, it is in PoC state, but further development is planned. Federation is achieved across RIs via Web-APIs (that can be used also for different purposes). Knowledge base and search engine of ENVRI Hub was presented by Zhiming Zhao. It uses a web crawler, then it extracts and indexes identified keywords (indexing pipeline) which is then used in the search engine. There are various possibilities on how to use the knowledge base (search, graph visualisation, in Jupyter notebooks, etc.).

Keith then presented again, this time the federated AAI and its architecture based on the AARC blueprint architecture. RIs can use any technology (but comply with some standards), no new IdP. It led to achieving the goals: harmonisation, federation, SSO, policies for managing authorization. Maggie Hellström explained the use of PIDs for linking different artifacts. Various key terms and their relations and use cases were explained: GUPRIs, challenge to support an appropriate “mix” of different PIDs, recommendations for PID allocation, contributions to EOSC PID Policy and PID Architecture, and inventory of “PID best practices”. The final presentation by Damien Boulanger wrapped-up the session with a science demonstrator related to FAIR ENVRI atmospheric data, i.e. how it all works together in ENVRI.

Tuesday, 21 March 2023

Opening Plenary Session: Welcome to RDA P20

21 March 2023, 9:00 - 10:30 CET, Conference Hall (Hallén), Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR/CERTH)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ/CTU)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- A round of introductory presentations, celebrating 10 years of RDA and stressing its importance & relevance.
- Sverker Holmgren moderated the session, reminded us that the conference is back in Göteborg after 10 years and added practical information.
- Lars Börjesson summarised the events of the first RDA meeting and then briefly introduced [Chalmers e-Commons](#) which is used for connecting local researchers and groups with national and international digital research infrastructures.
- Hilary Hanahoe described the development of RDA over the past 10 years, how it was built, its vision, mission, and guiding principles.
- The talk from an ECR (Madiareni Sulaiman): a clear challenge that is identified - and especially relevant for the Global South, is that sustainable solutions (such as open & FAIR data repositories) are not always available/accessible everywhere.
- Natasha Simons from ARDC summarised the shifts (not only) in the data landscape from an Australian perspective and how RDA helps to connect various national and international efforts, share expertise, and provide outputs that can be adopted and adapted (with real-world impact).
- Wilhelm Widmark from Stockholm University talked about Swedish Higher Education Institutions and how they are involved in Open Science (through EOSC but also national initiative - the [SND Network](#)). He also explain different approaches to EOSC implementation in Nordic countries.

RDA Plenary Session: Building RDA for the Future - Celebrating 10 years of the RDA

21 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:00 CET, Conference Hall (Hallen), Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR/CERTH)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- Panel conversation on the background of RDA - and the future
- John Wood: Seminal paper on Open Science: "[Riding the Wave. How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data](#)"
 - Written by journalist - knew how to write for politicians. Had a phenomenal impact in Europe!
- Beth Plale: Study from 2014 - Arranged RDA WG and IG on a scale from technically to socially oriented. More than 50% were socially oriented - eye-opening at the time!
- Connie Clare (RDA Community Development Manager). Handbook written as output from RDA WG: "[Engaging Researchers with Data Management. The cookbook.](#)"
- Ross Wilkinson:
 - We need experts in communicating the value of Open Science/Data to early career researchers
 - Also get informed by what the early career researchers value & need and bring this info further (making use of relevant expertise)
- Recommendations from John Woods to RDA members:
 - No more than 10 recommendations as WG output. Preferably a prime number!
 - Every person here should have a 15 second statement that they can make to a politician in a lift

Notes:

- John Wood: Seminal paper on Open Science:
 - "[Riding the Wave. How Europe can gain from the rising tide of scientific data](#)"
 - Written by journalist - knew how to write for politicians. Had a phenomenal impact in Europe!

- Ross Wilkinson:
 - On the process starting the RDA community
- Beth Plale:
 - 2014: Organised WG and IG on a scale from technically to socially oriented. More than 50% were socially oriented - eye-opening at the time!
- Julia Gehrmann (PhD student, Univ Cologne, Biomedical informatics):
 - First RDA plenary. A bit overwhelmed by the opportunities. Challenge of making use of clinical data for research. Seeing possibilities through the community.
- Kathryn Barker (RDA Community Manager, Australian RDC):
 - How to focus on the global south?
 - How to get in touch with organisations and leverage RDA?
- Connie Clare (RDA Community Development Manager):
 - Personally, a dream position. Building social and technical bridges. Inspired by RDA in my PhD. WG output: "[Engaging Researchers with Data Management. The cookbook.](#)"
 - Collaboration with Oracle for Research. Facilitate two Working Groups:
 - [Facilitating Open Data Publication, access, sharing, and publication](#)
 - Multi-omics

Pt2: are we there yet?

- John Woods
 - Data literacy should be taught in primary school. Everyone interprets data in a cultural context
- Julia Gehrmann:
 - Misconception about privacy infringement happening automatically when sharing data
 - Data protection should be supported so that data can be always shared compliantly
- Ross Wilkinson:
 - We need experts in communicating the value of Open Science/Data to early career researchers.
 - Ask the early career researchers what they value & need
 - Bring in expertise to bring the information further
 - Speed of engagement will need to rise in ways we cannot yet imagine
- John Woods:
 - Ireland was very important. Many important conversations in Irish pubs.
 - No more than 10 recommendations. Preferably a prime number!
 - Every person here should have a 15 second statement that they can make to a politician in a lift
 - Sabbatical year fundamental for understanding other cultures and how this reflects in data management and associated policies

RDA Plenary Session: Building Institutional Partnerships for the Future

21 March 2023, 13:00 - 13:55 CET, Conference Hall (Hallén), Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Highlights:

- Focus on the Open Science landscape in Latin America
- "[La referencia](#)" - national initiative formed by governments in South America
 - Federated network. Interoperating with global networks, repositories, etc
 - Open software platform - aggregation, quality, control of research data
 - Last year also adopted by Portugal. Expanding to Africa
 - Help of OpenAIRE was important to be internationally aligned
 - Looking for other international collaborations, such as with RDA
 - Spanish translation of RDA outputs - well received
 - Diagnosing training needs in all of spanish-speaking region in S.America
- Chile - boom of open science in area right now.
- [Ecuadorian Corporation for the Development of Research and the Academy \(CEDIA\)](#) central in Ecuador:
 - National research infrastructure network. Providing services to universities. Training of researchers in the topics related to RDM. Lack of funding of research, policies, etc.
- Brazil - State of São Paulo
 - Rich and stable funder. Supporting strong connection with RDA. First connection in Denver. Lots of help from different infrastructures, exchange ideas, etc.
 - Largest amount of users except the USA
- General:
 - Important with focus on two-way exchange in collaborating with Latin America
 - Latin America is very varied. Challenge that we are seen from the outside as a "big block"
 - Understand our own dynamics, different than other regions. Important to develop and adopt one's own dynamics

Notes:

- Eva:
 - Q: What have you been doing in the last 10 years in latin america, while RDA has been developing (little contribution from L. America, costly)
- Federico Cetrangolo (Grad. Economics and MS Administration and Public Policies, Argentina)
 - "[La referencia](#)" - national initiative formed by governments in South America. Visibility of open science contribution - contribute to world development
 - Federated network. Interoperating with global networks, repositories, etc
 - Open software platform - aggregation, quality, control of research data
 - Installable at each node of the network
 - Last year adopted by Portugal. Working in Africa
- Javier Valdiviezo (System Engineer specialist, Ecuador, CEDIA)
 - Increasing open scientific output
- Freddy Sumba (Early career, Computer Systems Engineer, CEDIA)
 - Focus on metadata for data repositories.
- Eva:
 - Experience from Chile - boom of open science in area right now.
 - Importance of common language? Possibility of common standards for the area?
- Federico Cetrangolo:
 - Focus on deposition of research papers in open repositories
 - Open data is getting more focus right now
 - La referencia
 - Help of OpenAIRE was important to be internationally aligned
 - Looking for other international collaborations, such as with RDA
 - Spanish translation of RDA outputs - well received
 - Diagnosing training needs in all of spanish-speaking region in S.America
- Javier Valdiviezo (System Engineer specialist, Ecuador, CEDIA)
 - CEDIA central in Ecuador
 - National research infrastructure (?) network. Providing services to universities. Training of researchers in the topics related to RDA. Lack of funding of research, policies, etc.
- Eva: Current status of technology?
- Freddy Sumba:
 - Federated repositories.
 - Problem is not technologies, but knowledge on RDM and sharing of that knowledge
- Adding 3 panel members from audience (ad hoc manner):
 - Claudia (Brazil), ...
 - Future of research data in Latin America and a global approach? Can we think about Latin America Open Science cloud?
- Federico Cetrangolo:

- Europe/China etc 2-3% of GDP on R&D, Latin America less than 1 %
- RDA is an important source of information on RDM
- Cultural change is necessary for open science. Best approach is to change incentives
- Claudia (RDA council, Brazil)
 - Sao Paolo. Rich and stable funder. Supporting strong connection with RDA. First connection in Denver. Lots of help from different infrastructures, exchange ideas, etc.
 - State of Sao Paolo, largest amount of users except the USA
- Alexandra(?):
 - Common source of funding is difficult.
 - Solutions should be global. Multi-language issues should be considered. Possible to study language models for translation.
- Leila (based in Germany for 40 yrs, from Columbia):
 - Language is an issue, but overcome-able in practice. Key is collaboration.
 - Should have more nodes in Latin America
 - Lots of data that can be brought into the international community. E.g. biodiversity. Of global importance.
- Javier Valdiviezo
 - Future is training researchers
- Freddy:
 - Data-driven research.
- Gabriella:
 - Experience from "La referencia" and others. Understand our own dynamics, different than other regions. Important to develop and adopt one's own dynamics.
 - The unification of "La referencia" gives us a different way to interact with RDA and other groups. Perhaps we can (as RDA) work with existing similar organizations elsewhere, e.g. Africa.
- From audience:
 - Time to change the narrative on latin america? Many consortia are set up in latin america. Open access is the mainstream. Leadership coming from the area.
- Alexandria:
 - Agree. Two way exchange. Training material, data, research outputs.
- Claudia:
 - Latin America is very varied. Challenge that we are seen from the outside as a "big block"

Data Management Planning: where are we and where do we want to be?

21 March 2023, 14:00 - 15:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Studio, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Active Data Management Plans IG](#) ✓, [DMP Common Standards WG](#) ↻, [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Paulette Lieby (FR)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- Mostly European participants. Several new to maDMP.
- Scope: identify new hot topics
- Pt1: intro to maDMPs
- Starting point: DMPs are mandatory
 - Automatic DMPs creation is crucial
 - Understand which stakeholder need to provide information at what stage (researcher, manager, funder)
 - 2019 recommendation (documentation on GitHub)
 - Not a questionnaire, not a template
 - A way of exchanging information. (glue across systems)
 - Using PIDs are controlled dictionaries
- Talk2: domain-specific guidance
 - Horizon DMP: researcher wants template and best practices
 - Examples, terminology
 - Survey for collecting info on demographics, data description, documentation, archiving,
 - Results: equal split across natural sciences, engineer, life sciences and humanities.
 - Research infrastr. And postdoc dominating the statistics
 - Issues w specific differences:
 - Standards
 - Types
 - Generation and collection

- Documentation
 - Framework
 - Issue with overlaps:
 - FAIR princ.
 - Storage
 - Naming
 - Issue with domain-specific focus
 - PID
 - Licenses
 - Learning material
- Prototype
 - Jupiter notebook
 - On GitHub
 - Also Google form, if desired
 - W guidance, to reach Zenodo eventually
 - Guidance from communities
 - 5 disciplines covered
 - 4 categories, but there is a desire to get very granular eventually
 - Questions:
 - Lack of FAIR principles
 - These are not “templates”, just recommendations ()
 - Struggle with maintenance
 - This will not be addressed at this stage
- Talk3: software manager plan
 - Machine-actionable SMP
 - Not currently described in DMPs.
 - Can be linked to a DMP.
 - Main scope: support traceability
 - Lack of funder requirement for SMP
 - maSMP on GitHub to support FAIR4RS
 - Q to audience: should DMP and SMP being separated or integrated
- Marek: maintenance of maDMP
 - Co-chair of standard
 - Several technical issues with specifications:
 - Not a single source of truth:
 - Figures, JSON schema, spreadsheet, README
 - Hard to contribute and version
 - No community stories
 - No automation - need to be more sustainable
- Talk5: DMP cross-fertilisation WS

- Awareness
- Diff. docus: institutions vs funders
- Review, evaluation, assessment
- Toolkit to engage researchers with DMPs

- Group A: Marek took proper notes
- Group B:
 - Cultural challenges for adopting DMPs and lack of training
 - How to really use DMPs as living documents
 - Ethics and sensitive data info appearing in multiple places
 - Distinction between DMPs for small and large projects

- Group C:
 - DMP and analysis? How to get help?
 - How DMP reflects concepts when there are multiple point of views (social science)
 - Do we need more than one template?
 - Decisions trees required
 - Different disciplines process DMPs differently

- Group D:
 - DMPs are very long, tricky to add SMP as well
 - Decision tree crucial (for domain-specific aspects)
 - Consensus: a DMP is not enough
 - Lack of awareness
 - No fear of sharing code

Summary (Paulette Lieby)

- A common session of three groups.
- A short overview of work so far (in particular, see RDA DMP CS <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard> recommendations, 2019)
- **Discussions**
 - The software management plan: do we want another template or integrate its features into the DMP
 - The maintenance of the RDA DMP CS: Marek Suchanek got an EOSC future grant for that work
 - A jupyter notebook https://santoshilam.github.io/Discipline_Specific_Guidance_for_DMPs/intro.html has

been setup to gather community input to enrich the discipline-specific guidance for DMPs material; their survey has been published

<https://zenodo.org/record/7391669#.ZBnBmo7MJD8>

- see <https://zenodo.org/record/7414450#.ZBnBro7MJD9> for the RDA for Data Management Planning Community Cross-fertilisation Workshop Summary

- **Questions and future discussions**

- How to maintain all community-issued material
- How to handle generic vs specific questions and topics within the DMP

Coordinating mechanisms for making code visible

21 March 2023, 14:00 - 15:30 CET, [event link](#), Tesla room, Lindholmen Conference Centre.

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR/CERTH)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR/CERTH)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- The session focused primarily on discussing the existing mechanisms to make code visible with the RDA community. There was a direct connection to relevant outputs (FAIR₄RS) and communities (such as ReSA and FORCE₁₁).
- There are already some concrete efforts (and outcomes) to address the challenges in software citation, but there is always room for more contributors (and adopters)! However, there is still reluctance in sharing (both code and data)

- 86% of researchers are reluctant to share data, code or both. Only a 4% of the results were reproducible, we need to improve. The FAIR principles can (and should) be used as guidance. Ultimately, matching data with the code is a critical issue for reproducibility
- Key messages:
 - Incentives are huge and make a difference
 - There is still reluctance to share (we need culture change, need more incentives, improve the lack of knowledge)
 - Best practices are there, like the many mechanisms cited in this session, we need more culture change
 - New guidelines, specific for those who are new to developing code for research
 - Training sessions are required to improve how we make code visible

Notes:

- [Collaborative notes](#)
-

What is happening in the Semantic interoperability realm and in VSSIG?

21 March 2023, 14:00 - 15:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Lobby, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Vocabulary Services IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO) 14:45->

Reported by:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- The Vocabulary and Semantic Services Interest Group (VSSIG) is asking for new co-chairs and wants to reinstate regular meetings
- Overview of Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT)
 - Interoperability between ontologies, focus on reuse of machine-operable variable descriptions
 - Recommendations published May 2022: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00071>
 - Implementations to be presented in WG session, March 22 (below)
- Updates of the Ontoportalliance
 - New technologies:
 - O'FAIRe: Ontology FAIRness Evaluator
 - Native support of SSSOM (brand new mapping repository)

- Upcoming [FAIR-IMPACT](https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/why-mappings-matter-and-how-make-them-fair) workshop mentioned by Yann Le Franc:
<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/why-mappings-matter-and-how-make-them-fair> (Apr 13, presentations available)

Notes:

- [Collaborative notes](#)
- The Vocabulary and Semantic Services Interest Group (VSSIG) mission is:
 - To form a network of experts in the realm of Semantic Web and Linked Data, to share and discuss new technologies, controversial concepts, new ideas, and existing recommendations.
 - Goal: to develop community-based approaches and recommendations for the development and use of FAIR semantic artefacts across domains
- Asking for new co-chairs!
- Want to reinstate regular meetings
- Working group: Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminologies (I-ADOPT)
 - Focus: Interoperability between ontologies
 - Recommendations published May 2022: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00071>
 - General recommendations for the description of variables
 - Catalog of terminologies for reuse in I-ADOPT variables on GitHub; including a unit-to-property lookup
 - Metadata templates: Nanopublication, CEDAR
 - Implementations to be presented in WG session, March 22
- Task groups:
 - Minimum Metadata Task Group - C. Jonquet/L. Bonino
 - Terms and Concept Recommendations
- Ideas for new task groups:
 - Semantic mappings
 - Mid-level vocabularies for interoperability (e.g. Quality)
 - Promote interoperability (How to choose vocabularies and ontologies, Upper level ontologies, How to make semantics more usable)
- Ontological approaches for Digital Twins
 - Developed in domain of Oceanography
 - A digital twin is a virtual representation of a physical asset enabled through data and simulators for real-time prediction, optimization, monitoring, controlling, and improved decision making.
 - A DT differs from a traditional (modelling) tool as it is interoperable and federated and designed with user interactivity in mind.
- The Semantic Interoperability Task Force of the EOSC Association: Experiences and ongoing activities (Wolmar N. Åkerström)
 - (Meta)data standards (Theme 1)

- Survey the landscape of semantic interoperability around EOSC
- Propose a minimum set of (meta)data, indicators and crosswalks (started 2023)
- Semantic artefact catalogues (Theme 2)
 - Converge on a definition and the dimensions of a maturity model
 - Analyse catalogues using the model and suggest a path forward (started 2023)
- Use cases (Theme 3)
 - Capturing interoperability case studies from EOSC stakeholders
 - Indexing and presenting use cases to adopters and builders (started 2023)
- Updates of the Ontoportalliance
 - 11 different ontology portals, including:
 - BioPortal, MedPortal, AgroPortal
 - Biodiversity portal as one of 3 new portals
 - Aim: Making OntoPortal a real open source project
 - New technologies:
 - O'FAIRe: Ontology FAIRness Evaluator
 - Enhanced SKOS support
 - Native support of SSSOM (brand new mapping repository)
 - + more
- FAIR-Impact
 - WP4 expected outcomes:
 - Broader and more harmonised use of semantic artefacts in EOSC.
 - Guidelines to collect and curate research software metadata. (CODEMETA for example)
 - A framework for metadata crosswalks and mappings between semantic artefacts.(workshops and collection of practical uses cases/tools)
 - Use of semantic artefacts within data repositories for better data search and indexing.
 - Bundling of data with RO-crate
 - T4.2: Minimum metadata for Semantic artefacts (Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran)
 - T4.4: Crosswalks and mapping (Yann Le Franc)
 - Upcoming [FAIR-IMPACT](https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/why-mappings-matter-and-how-make-them-fair) workshop mentioned by Yann Le Franc:
<https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/why-mappings-matter-and-how-make-them-fair> (Apr 13, presentations available)

RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 2

21 March 2023, 16:00 - 17:30 CET

Infrastructure supporting the FAIR data principles in life science research practice

21 March 2023, 16:00 - 17:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Lobby, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#) ✓, [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#) ↻

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Paulette Lieby (FR)
- Allyson Lister (UK)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Paulette Lieby (FR)
- Allyson Lister (UK)

Highlights:

- The IG Chairs propose to move forward on the development of Guidelines for FAIR Improvement that Life Science Infrastructures anywhere in the world can utilise.
- IG Chairs will email all existing group members and those who have indicated their email address is this document - with a message to:
 1. invite others to join the monthly meetings and activities,
 2. Inform members about the intended work survey.
 3. further clarify what types of digital assets are managed by various Life Science Data Infrastructures
 4. invite ideas for what IG members would like the IG to focus on through a survey
- The IG Charter should also be reviewed.

Notes:

[Collaborative notes](#)

Second plenary.

Focus: how infrastructure solves challenges on behalf of the user.

- FAIRsharing WG: Outputs and related activities of the WG over the past year
 - FAIRsharing registry: updates, including new metadata fields for policies and databases to align with RDA recommendations and other community outputs
 - The FAIRsharing [Community Champions Programme](#), which is supported by the RDA / EOSC Future through the Domain Ambassadorship awarded to Allyson Lister, and which draws upon the collective expertise from the RDA and EOSC.

- Survey on infrastructures for FAIR data
 - 13 infrastructures from different areas
 - 50% mature
 - Few in development
 - Metrics using the data life cycle
 - Analyse not scoring good (which is not unexpected)
 - Flnability issue, enter infrastructures in registry such as FAIRsharing

Summary (Paulette)

- The LS Data infrastructures IG, started 2022: ELIXIR to reach beyond Europe
- FAIRsharing Registry WG: a repository of cross-disciplinary curated standards and guidelines
- The question: how mature are global infrastructures in implementing FAIR DM?
 - A survey: of 10-20 infrastructures, to be published
- Answers: 6 flash talks
 - USA: Valentina Di Francesco, National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI) Chief Data science Strategist and Director of the Office of Genomic Data Science (in person)
 - USA: Dawei Lin, Associate Director for Bioinformatics & Senior Advisor to the Director at DAIT, NIAID, NIH to speak about ImmPort (in person)
 - USA: Lindsey Anderson, Computational Scientist (US Department of Energy Pacific Northwest National Laboratory) (virtual/online)
 - Europe: Joel Hedlund, Head of AIDA Data Hub —offering Data Sharing, Policy Support, and Services for researchers in Swedish medical imaging AI (virtual/online)
 - Africa: Sumir Panji, Network (Bioinformatics) Manager at H3ABioNet (recorded)
 - Australia: Gareth Price, Science Lead of Galaxy Australia (recorded)
- Services like data sharing, controlled access, computing platform, tools, archiving, With high interoperability, FAIR assessment.
Of note: data sharing of sensitive data: AIDA data sharing policy (Sweden) and H3ABioNet Africa.

Working with PIDS in Tools and e-infrastructures: Three concrete examples

21 March 2023, 16:00 - 17:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Studio, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Working with PIDS in Tools IG](#) +

Planned attendees:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Reported by:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- Session focused mainly on prioritising the future of IG.
- Presented case studies of use of PIDs: DMPtool, CSIRO, DataCite and Workflows
 - Maria Praetzelis (UC3) presented the use of PIDs within DMPTool and integration in RSpace / DataVerse.
 - Jens Klump (CSIRO) presented how to associate [IGSNs](#) (PIDs for samples) with sample data using FAIMS and [RSpace](#) tools.
 - Xiaoli Chen from DataCite provided an update on the FAIR Workflows Project involving incorporation of DataCite DOIs into tools used throughout the research lifecycle. She presented integrations with [ChronosHub](#), [Dryad](#), and ARDC/[RAiD](#). The integration with DMPTool has been mentioned again.

The Ethics of AI and Data Visitation: Building Blocks for Data Commons and Open Science

21 March 2023, 16:00 - 17:30 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR/CERTH)

Reported by:

- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR/CERTH)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

Collaborative notes: [The Ethics of AI and Data Visitation: Building Blocks for Data Commons and Open Science collaborative notes - Google Docs](#)

- More of an overview of the current situation. It also led to an ad-hoc meet-up on the next day, around ethics.
- There are a lot of documents on Ethics and AI produced and published by China
- We should be re-using a lot of these, as they provide a clear framework of considerations - both technical and regulatory.

Wednesday, 22 March 2023

RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 3

22 March 2023, 9:00 - 10:30 CET

Sensitive data contexts and disciplines: A look at different approaches

22 March 2023, 9:00 - 10:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Lobby, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Sensitive Data IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org) Paulette Lieby (FR)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

Summary (Paulette)

Sensitive data across disciplines: level of awareness, barriers, and risk management

- Overview of IG
 - Since 2020 BoF, 2021 IG
 - 2022: work on vocabulary gathering, 2023: work on glossary, as a living document
 - Objective: developing a shared understanding of sensitive data terms
- 3 presentations from social science, astronomy, life sciences (from LS infra IG)
 - Of note:
 - Astronomy is always open data, possibly with a publication embargo to mitigate competition (observation times are precious and must be planned well in advance) ; `as open as possible, closed only if really necessary`
 - Sensitive data awareness is well shared
 - Barriers to sharing: highly risk adverse
 - Risk management:
 - the model The Five Safes (from <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>)
 - GA4GH a great enabler
 - Building trust: building trusted research environments
 - Conclusion:
 - balance "risks to share data" vs "risks not to share data"

Defining the roadmap towards FAIR for Machine Learning

22 March 2023, 9:00 - 10:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Studio, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR4ML\) IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR, CERTH)

Reported by:

- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR, CERTH)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

Collaborative notes: [Defining the roadmap towards FAIR for Machine Learning collaborative notes - Google Docs](#)

- Significant participation ~60 people (40 F2F and 20 virtually)
- Clear interest on both standards (DOME was presented), metadata setup (for machine-actionable efforts) as well as interoperable platforms for sharing ML models (registries)
- Machine-actionable metadata vocabularies for ML models and ML dataset is a short-term activity to be discussed

Expanding our horizons to new disciplines: harmonising on what is core to all

22 March 2023, 9:00 - 10:30 CET, [event link](#), Decibel room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Reported by:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- [A Catalogue of Groups involved in Physical Samples and Identifiers](#)
- Lightning talks on new projects/updates on existing ones (should have been 20 minutes, went way over time)
- Deep Dive: Biospecimens in the Life Sciences: a new proposed group (Did unfortunately not have enough time to present properly...)
 - [Working group proposal](#)

- **Goals:**
 - Define the minimum set of attributes required for describing biospecimens in the Life Sciences (Minimal Information About a Biological Sample, MIABS) with ontological mapping for semantic unambiguity and machine actionability.
 - Identify the required attributes for registering persistent identifiers for biospecimens.
 - Define the implementation specifics for integration of biospecimen Fair Digital Objects with operational infrastructure; for example, e-Infrastructures, repositories, and machines.

Notes:

[Collaborative notes](#)

Computational Reproducibility: What's Next for RDA?

22 March 2023, 9:00 - 10:30 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- **Goal:** forming an IG or WG
 - Interesting ideas about certification of reproducibility if studies
 - Focus on analysis, but should not also data production via computational methods be reproducible (this was not expanded upon, possibly not of interest for the group)
 - Struggle defining to what extent complex and long analysis will need to be reproduced.
 - **Issue:** great competence required, possibly large computational facilities
-

RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 4

22 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET

Promoting synergies between national RDM and data stewardship networks

22 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Studio, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Paulette Lieby (FR)

Reported by:

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Paulette Lieby (FR)

Highlights:

- Highlight₁

Notes:

- [Collaborative notes](#)
- Presentation on various RDM networks:
 - Irish Data Stewardship Network “Sonraí”: they plan to launch a website soon (<https://datastewards.ie/>), organise ongoing series of roadshows and plan a national conference
 - RDM in The Netherlands: different networks already in place ([DTL DS IG](#), [Health-RI DSC](#), [4TU ResearchData Community](#), [RDNL](#), [LCDRM](#), [DANS](#), [OSC-NL](#)) that are also already interconnected.
 - Live Kvale presented Data managers networks in Norway: RDA-Norway, GIDA Sapmi, Dataverse NO, Bergen Research Data Network, University of Oslo Data Managers Network, LS RDM group Norway, and Data curator network for FAIR research data. UiT Data Stewards Network is in the startup phase. They keep low maintenance, host meetups and communicate via mailing lists, Slack, Teams and use Google docs.
 - In Italy, they combine top-down national context (legislation on Open Access, National Plan for Open Science, [ANVUR](#)) and bottom-up support ([ICDI](#), [AISA](#), [ITRN](#)). They want to kick-start a national bottom-up network.
 - In Canada, they have the [Digital Research Alliance of Canada](#) which connects experts from different institutions.
 - From Austria, three different models were presented (Data Steward Contact Point from Medical University of Graz, Data Steward Office as used at TU Wien and University of Innsbruck, and Data Steward Network as at TU Graz and University of Vienna). They also have the project FAIR Data Austria (lead by TU Graz). At Uni Vienna, they also have a certificate course “[Data Steward](#)” with 5 modules, 15 ECTS credits in total.
 - Then, there was a discussion of participants about importance of RDM networks, their goals, steps, and key stakeholders.

Summary (Paulette)

Presentations around RDM networks in several countries (Ireland, Canada, Austria, NL, Italy, Norway).

Topics discussed:

- Define the objectives of the network, what is its purpose
- An institutional, regional, national, international network?
- Issues around sustainability over time
- A top-down or bottom-up network
- Creating a network from scratch or building on existing resources
- Examples: ELIXIR, EOSC, RDA, others...

Conclusion: this BoF wants the discussion pursued.

Develop actionable guidelines from the data versioning principles

22 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET, [event link](#), Decibel room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Data Versioning IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini (only part of the session)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

Not a particularly well attended session. A lot of focus on Figcite and Zenodo. There is a desire for more machine-actionability. (honestly, a bit difficult to pick up many points for people not involved in this group)

RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 5

22 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET

Evaluation of Research

22 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET, [event link](#), Tesla room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by: Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- This BoF session was mainly about reasoning why evaluation of research is now relevant and how important it is (also in scope of RDA).
 - Focused on ways other than traditional metrics, eg publication based
 - Also to recognise roles and practical work done towards a research output
 - There are already some relevant RDA groups (e.g. SHARC IG or Data Usage Metrics WG) but it seems that some group covering or putting together various research evaluation methods is missing.
 - There will probably be a strong link with [CoARA](#) and other related initiatives.
-

Community Engagement That Works! Examining tools and success stories of pathways to Engagement in Community-led organisations at a global level

22 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Lobby, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#) ↻, [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#) ✓, [Early Career and Engagement IG](#) ✓, [Engaging Researchers with Data IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR, CERTH)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Allyson Lister (UK)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Reported by:

- Allyson Lister (UK)

Highlights:

Key takeaways were (especially within the context of how ELIXIR might approach community engagement tasks):

- Recognition of the importance of coordinated community engagement (and the importance of Community Engagement Managers as sustained rather than ad hoc positions with clearly defined roles).
- Improvements are needed to improve findability of RDA outputs
- Community building often starts with volunteers working with specific, defined audiences. When resistance to advocacy efforts are encountered, those volunteers might feel there's nowhere to turn for support. The RDA (*AL note: perhaps EOSC/ELIXIR training as well?*) should be the place to turn for encouragement and reassurance.

- There is a clear benefit to both the RDA and the European/EOSC-funded Domain Ambassadors to provide space within RDA to continue to connect post-funding, and to provide insight and guidance for successful outreach and engagement activities to potential future globally funded ambassadorships.

Notes:

- See notes at <https://docs.google.com/document/d/15qid1Y5Eij5CY8cVT99z9DHzyTVUb7q63gpiFgR6oQ/edit?usp=sharing>

IG FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Discussing the FAIR DO Concept

22 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Nick Juty (UK)
- Carole Goble (UK)

Reported by:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- Aim: "FAIR DOs for Pedestrians":
 - FAIR DO elevator pitches, tutorials, presentations collected in [Google Drive](#)
- FNDO: FAIR non-data objects (Daniel S Katz):
 - A failing of FAIR was its bias towards data and just data, at a detailed level – FAIR DO seems to be repeating this
 - FAIR for Research Software (FAIR₄RS) WG
 - FAIR for Machine Learning IG (FAIR₄ML)
 - [Kick-off last plenary](#)
- [FAIR-IMPACT open calls for support](#) (deadline June 1st 2023):
 - #1: FAIRness assessment challenge
 - #2: Enabling FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate for content/metadata discovery and consumption
 - Increase the discoverability of the metadata and content, through a combination of two approaches; RO-Crate (archiving/bundling with a 'manifest') and Signposting (html based simple pointers). These two approaches are being used in combination as a pragmatic approach to

making digital scholarly/research objects more FAIR. This also integrates schema.org/bioschemas approaches

- Estimated five days of effort over a one month period, most likely in early autumn 2023.

Notes:

[Collaborative session notes](#)

Comment from Sveinung Gundersen: The session was a bit hard to grasp for newcomers to the FAIR DO details – the discussion assumed background knowledge and seemed mostly for the insiders. I left half-way through. The last point in the highlights above is extracted from the collaborative sessions notes as it happened after I left.

RDA Plenary Session: Building Industrial Partnerships for the Future

22 March 2023, 15:30 - 17:00 CET, Conference Hall (Hallen), Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Notes:

Oracle and potential for hosting genomics data. What is ELIXIR's take on this? (Bianchini)

Thursday, 23 March 2023

RDA Plenary Session: Building Platform Partnerships for the Future

23 March 2023, 09:00 - 10:30 CET, Conference Hall (Hallen), Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR, CERTH)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Reported by: Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- Deliang Cheng (Uni Gothenburg) presented the role of data/model in climate science (which combines meteorology, physics, chemistry, and geography). The development in this field of science is highly driven by societal and political needs but also technology. [IPCC](#) helps as common data/model frameworks and formats are essential for international and trans-disciplinary climate research.
- Mikiko Tanifuji (National Institute of Informatics, Japan) talked about their experience with interoperability in research projects in terms of FAIR. Global Open Research Commons IG has been mentioned in terms of providing essential elements for interoperability. Japan has a nation-wide open science infrastructure [NII RDC](#) (which is IT-driven) as well as domain-specific research data platforms such as [DICE](#) for materials science. Within NII RDC, machine-actionable DMPs are used for automation of data management processes thanks to interoperability.
- Tshiamo Motshegwa presented the [African Open Science Platform](#) (AOSP) where one of the biggest challenges is international interoperability and cross-border data management.
- Dirk Pleiter (KTH.se) presented integration of HPC and data infrastructures in terms of history, present, and future. There are several challenges toward HPC Data Centres, mainly support for collaborative research, wider access, more complex workflows leading to federated e-infrastructure. There are also some challenges that always been there but with federated environment those are even more important, e.g. access control and security.

RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 6

23 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET

The Role of Middleware in Data and Metadata Management: National and Institutional Approaches Involving iRODS and Alternatives

23 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET, [event link](#), Tesla room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Reported by: Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- Highlight₁

Notes:

- [Collaborative Notes](#)
- There was a brief introduction on Research Data Architectures for Research Institutions (RDARI) and middleware in RDM. The term middleware was explained as a glue connecting different platforms and devices together.
- Ingrid Barcena Roig (KU Leuven) presented ManGO which is a RDM platform based on iRODS. Users can login to ManGO portal (and other clients) using SSO and then manage data via iRODS. In ManGO, users manage the related metadata that can be then used to efficiently search. It also offers ACL (permissions) in order to make data reusable.
- Maithili Kalamkar Stam talked about iRODS-based data middleware used at SURF. They utilise iRODS on their VMs and also use YODA web portal and other services. Other features such as encryption, redundancy, backups, monitoring via Grafana, or SSO are also provided.
- Michele Carpena (CINECA) presented a status report of EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure, mainly how different EUDAT services (B2HANDLE, B2ACCESS, B2DROP etc.) support the research environment.
- A discussion about various middleware topics followed, mainly different experiences of participants with iRODS and other relevant services/technologies.

Data Repository Attributes Working Group (DRAWG) Working Meeting

23 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Data Repository Attributes WG](#) ✓

Planned attendees:

- Allyson Lister (UK)

Reported by:

- Allyson Lister (UK)

Highlights:

- Feedback from 'critical friends' confirmed that this work is needed and early draft has promise
- There is still work done to improve the documentation in a range of areas
- We have a highly engaged WG who are committed to working together to make this as useful as possible for all stakeholders, and there is appetite to do this work in the coming months.
- ELIXIR may wish to engage with the attributes via commenting on the first full draft to ensure it aligns with our best practices and any internal criteria we may have.

Notes:

Collaborative session notes:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pCgcCBkMdQW8qlhx-ddnT6FBUTXsmxzcbiQL2NFIV84/edit?usp=sharing>

Brokering Framework - Update and Finalisation

23 March 2023, 11:00 - 12:30 CET, [event link](#), Kelvin room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Brokering Framework WG](#)

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Reported by:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- The session provided an overview of the outcomes from the Brokering Framework WG, which is wrapping up (aims to publish as RDA output by next plenary).
 - Most important is a conceptual model detailing the many aspects to consider for a brokering framework, a standard and registry for brokering and mediation components, and a set of recommendations for implementation.
 - The Brokering Framework metadata schema should be a superset of [Proposal for a pragmatic flexible Semantic Mapping Framework \(SEMAF\)](#), developed in EOSC context
- Several use cases were presented, of which the most important seems to be the EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalks registry (MSCR), as well as the EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR). These are two of the nine new services being developed in the FAIRCORE₄EOSC project (coordinated by CSC – IT Center for Science, Finland), 2022-2025. Some details on MSCR:
 - Implementation will be based on the Finnish Interoperability Platform

- Crosswalks & mapping support is supposed to range from csv tables, XSLT, X3ML to OWL, but the preferred approaches are RDF, JSON-LD and SSSOM.
- Issues highlighted by the presenters: mediations are reversible, that some mediations are non-commutative and that metadata aggregations may harm data discovery
- Another issue raised by the audience is whether MSCR will provide the actual running of the crosswalks (answer: it will not, but crosswalks can be downloaded and should be machine operable)
- As a follow-up to the last point, a discussion arose on whether this top-down approach to defining crosswalks will work in the real world when applied on real datasets or whether bottom-up, data-centric approaches would be more pragmatic (e.g. [whyqd](#), [omnipy](#), ...)

Notes:

- [Collaborative session notes](#)
- Brokering Framework WG Wrapping Up:
 - Aim to Publish as RDA Output by Next Plenary
 - Outcomes:
 - Conceptual model for a Brokering Framework
 - A set of recommendations and best practices for implementation
 - Brokering and mediation component description standard
 - Registry of brokering and mediation components (with important components that are currently operational)
 - Testing the registry in the context of real-life applications
 - Three mediation functions:
 - Semantic Transformation
 - Schematic Transformation ('Technical Interoperability')
 - Syntactic Transformation ('Technical Interoperability')
 - Metadata considerations:
 - Proposal based on the DataCite schema, with extensions. DataCite provides a crosswalk to schema.org.
 - Use of existing vocabularies wherever possible – six new vocabularies are needed in the current form
 - The Brokering Framework metadata schema should be a superset of Proposal for a pragmatic flexible Semantic Mapping Framework (SEMAF), developed in EOSC context
- Use cases:
 - FAIRCORE₄EOSC
 - 10 million EUR
 - Duration: June 2022 – May 2025
 - Consortium: 22 partners, coordinated by CSC – IT Center for Science

- Website: faircore4eosc.eu
- 9 core components to be implemented:
 - EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph)
 - EOSC PID Graph (PIDGraph)
 - EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)
 - EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)
 - EOSC PID Meta Resolved (PIDMR)
 - EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)
 - EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service (RAID)
 - EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors
 - EOSC Software Heritage Mirrors (SWHM)
- EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)
 - Data types as simple or complex as necessary
 - Each type will be provided with a PID and a common set of metadata
 - Validation schemas for types
- EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)
 - Publishing, discovery and access of metadata schemas and crosswalks (PID, metadata)
 - Mechanism to operationalise metadata conversions by combining crosswalks
 - GUI for visually creating crosswalks
 - Typing metadata schema's elements and attributes using registered data-types and data-type converters for format conversion in DTR
 - Crosswalks & mapping support ranging from csv tables, XSLT, X3ML to OWL.
 - RDF, JSON-LD and SSSOM are the preferred approaches.
 - Will be based on the Finnish Interoperability Platform
 - Issues: not all mediations are reversible and some mediations are non-commutative.
 - Metadata aggregations may harm data discovery (Daan Broeder), i.e. losing disciplinary detail.
- FAIR-IMPACT WP6: Interoperability
 - Agree and implement a common set of rules to ensure data and services within EOSC support interoperability.
 - Promoting the use and alignment towards existing specifications, standards or infrastructure, endorsed by the various scientific communities, as well as non-scientific larger data sources of interest to research.
- EOSC Task Force - Technical Interoperability
 - Alignment with historical use cases: SAEON, GEO Data Access Broker, SEMAF + RDA Metadata Crosswalks, PresQT

RDA Plenary 20th Meeting Breakout 7

23 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET

TRUST Principles & Certification updates

23 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET, [event link](#), Pascal room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Reported by: X Y (node/org)

- Federico Bianchini (NO)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

Part of RDA TIGER

Comm-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy technical repository service providers

- Meeting needs of technical service providers
- Enabling service certification
- Looking for members to write the case statement
-

Presentation CoreTrustSeal:

- Make the digital worlds reliable
- TRUST principles enabling this
- Core TRUST seal as a middle certification between nestor and ISO.
- Multiple stakeholders
- Enabling FAIR over time (check for obsolescence)
- Volunteer board
 - Looking for new members
- Peer-review type of system (volunteer-based)
- CTS: no profit, domain agnostic
- Process: self-assessment followed by peer review
 - Open peer review, look at other services
 - Align with best-practices
- 1000 euros for 3 years
- 2023-25 revision

- RDA progressively more involved
- Youtube channel with plenty of training
- When you have the seal, you can become a reviewer
- The same requirements for general and domain-specific repos

TRUST talk

- List of principles
- Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, Technology
- FAIR is for data, TRUST for the associated services

Data Granularity Guidance - Going Once, Going Twice,...

23 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET, [event link](#), Tesla room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Data Granularity WG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Reported by:

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)

Highlights:

- Data Granularity WG is nearing completion
- Output is a recommendations/guidance document of data granularity approaches for prioritised use cases, including terminology, methods to evaluate approaches, and summary of community feedback. In addition the WG output includes a set of collected use cases (in both [Excel](#) and [PDF](#) formats). Overview of current recommendations in notes (below)
- Participants provided feedback to the recommendations through post-it notes / jamboard

Notes:

[Collaborative session notes](#)

- Data Granularity WG is nearing completion
- **Mission:**
 - How to best support data granularity, providing guidance to determine the best level of granularity for user discovery, access, interoperability and citability.
 - Build upon existing RDA work (e.g. Data Citation WG, Publishing Data Services WG, Data Versioning WG)
 - Output:
 - Collected use cases (in both [Excel](#) and [PDF](#) formats)

- Recommendations document of data granularity approaches for prioritised use cases, including terminology, methods to evaluate approaches, and summary of community feedback.
 - **Current recommendations:**
 - **1. Metadata Schemas & Content**
 - a. Document granularity type and relationships, in particular hierarchical relationship, as part of the metadata scheme
 - b. Dimension/structural metadata fields should be clear, consistent, comprehensive and interoperable
 - **2. Policy**
 - a. Specify granularity in data policies and data guidance documents whenever possible
 - b. Repositories and/or disciplines should define consistent notions of dimensions and segmentation for datasets to better facilitate workflows and comparable metrics.
 - **3. Discovery & Access**
 - a. Leverage the dimension metadata for discovery via filtering and sorting features.
 - b. Use metadata level with the richest metadata for general discovery
 - c. Subsets should be represented in a query store that records dimensions that characterise the subset.
 - **4. Citation**
 - a. All granularity levels (collection, datasets, subsets) must be independently citable with a persistent identifier and resolvable landing pages.
 - b. By citing a collection, this should also count as a citation on the collection itself and for each collection hierarchically below it down to a specific dataset.
 - c. Customised identification of subsets and collection should be possible.
 - Participants were able to provide feedback and further input to recommendations via an interactive exercise with post-its in the room and a jamboard for those online.
-

Open Science Graph - Interoperability Framework. A debriefing from the Task Force

23 March 2023, 13:30 - 15:00 CET, [event link](#), Visual Arena Lobby, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Groups: [Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG](#) ✓

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)
- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)

Reported by: Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- Highlight1

Notes:

- [Collaborative Notes](#)
 - The session started with a presentation about Open Science Graphs (and/or SKGs - Scholarly Knowledge Graphs), mainly in terms of interoperability. There are already many SKGs/OSGs containing overlapping, partially interconnected, and interlinkable information. With an interoperability layer, SKG federation can be achieved.
 - There is now a group striving to create a WG for SKGs interoperability framework. Some work is already done, e.g. survey of common entities in data models of existing selected SKGs. Based on that, they already built a core SKG data model. There are still many questions and tasks to be done or even kicked off. The interoperability framework is being documented here: <https://skg-if.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
 - The discussion was then driven by prepared questions via Mentimeter, mainly around ideas about SKGs, their role, connections, use cases, and definitions.
-

RDA Closing Plenary

23 March 2023, 15:30 - 16:30 CET, Conference Hall (Hallen), Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees:

- Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (SE/NBIS)
- Fotis Psomopoulos (GR, CERTH)

Highlights:

- Next RDA Plenary will take place alongside International Data Week (IDW) 2023. The dates and location for this are: 23–26 October 2023, Salzburg, Austria.

Friday, 24 March 2023

Data-driven life science and the RDA

24 March 2023, 9:00 - 13:00 CET, [event link](#), Tesla room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Sveinung Gundersen (NO)
- Federico Bianchini (NO)
- Paulette Lieby (FR)

Notes:

(Paulette)

- Connecting life science infrastructures
- **“The FAIRsharing journey in RDA” by Susanna-Assunta Sansone**
 - From BioSharing to FAIRSharing
 - Omics data sharing 2009
 - Registry (standards, dbs, policies) 2011
 - 2015 RDA WG
 - 2016 BioSharing an Elixir resource
 - 2017 FAIRsharing: beyond LS due to RDA communities
 - From 2022, FAIRsharing community champions programme via EOSC future; collaborators recognised via ORCID; now infographics
- **“FAIRtracks WG in the making” by Ari Asmi & Sveinung Gundersen**
 - A selection of large consortia producing genomic data over the last 20 years
 - With largely incompatible models
 - Genomic tracks
 - Unified model for data analysis
 - Tracks in this broader sense covers many common file formats
 - What is special with track files
 - Routinely generated through standard pipelines
 - Represent summary of raw data
 - → data-driven discovery of genomic datasets with sub-dataset granularity
 - Timeline
 - 2010 genomic hyperbrowser
 - 2017 prototype of data import tool from data portals
 - 2018-20 ELIXIR implementation study
 - 2020 ...
 - 2022-23: going global with RDA TIGER

- **“Ask not what the RDA can do for you, ask what you can do for the RDA”**
by **Rory Macneil**
 - Rspace research space; integrated research infrastructure
 - Eg University College London
 - RDA: PIDs in Tools IG, RDARI IG, GORC Intl Model WG, EOSC future/RDA grant: working with Datacite to develop recommendations for best practices in incorporation PIDs into research tools
 - <https://www.researchspace.com/> (private)
 - Interaction as a company?

- **“FAIR Cookbook: pharmas and academia join forces - a role for RDA?”**
by **Susanna-Assunta Sansone**
 - Pharmas and academia join force: a role for RDA?
 - Operational for FAIR LS, but not only
 - Come with maturity levels (RDA FDMM)
 - Organising according to need
 - Credit and citability via ORCID
 - Motivations
 - Need specific examples
 - Do we bring this resource to RDA?
 - How?

- **“Australian BioCommons”** by **Jeff Christiansen**
 - To support LS communities with community scale infras
 - Different types of experience
 - Funded through NCRIS (Federal Gov)
 - Work with national infra providers to answer research needs
 - Since 4 years
 - Building relationships in the biodata space

- **“ELIXIR RDA Activities Focus Group”** by **Gavin Farrell**
 - ELIXIR focus group
 - Address emerging issues of interest
 - 10 focus groups
 - To make sure we work with the global RDA community
 - LS focused but cross-disciplinary
 - Further synergies: EOSC
 - See slides on Zenodo

Research Software workshop: guidelines and metrics for metadata curation

24 March 2023, 9:00 - 12:00 CET, [event link](#), Decibel room, Lindholmen Conference Centre

Planned attendees: X Y (node/org)

- Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Reported by: Marek Suchánek (CZ, CTU/IOCB)

Highlights:

- There are existing guidelines related to research software: [SIRS report recommendations](#), [FAIR4RS principles](#) and [CodeMeta initiative vocabulary](#).
- [Software Heritage](#) can be used for archiving of research software (in FAIR manner)

Notes:

During the initial introduction to the workshop, Morane Gruenpeter (Software Heritage) and Niel Chue Hong (Software Sustainability Institute) presented an overview of the current landscape and work done. Basically, there were two main areas or topics for the workshop. First, metadata vocabularies and related tools for describing research software such as [FAIR4RS principles](#), [CodeMeta](#), or [SIRS report recommendations](#). Second, the actual metrics for FAIR research software. In the interactive part, there were two groups focusing each on one of these two topics.

The first (A) group was further split to smaller groups where people discussed assigned metadata properties and answered related questions / described specific attributes and use cases. The second (B) group discussed metrics for FAIR research software, e.g. how they can be used to improve each principle of FAIR4RS, or what are the criteria for trustworthy research software repositories. Then, the final part of the workshop summarised the outputs of both groups and a brief discussion followed: ([meeting notes](#)).